

Representing Subalternity: A Study of Mahasweta Devi's Short Story "Draupadi"

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ABSTRACT

Mahasweta Devi's short story "Draupadi," translated by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, depicts a tale that explores both subaltern resistance and feminist assertion. The story centres on Dopdi Mejhen, a tribal woman who transforms from a victim of patriarchal and colonial violence to a symbol of resistance against state oppression subverting hegemonic power structures. This paper critically examines the short story through the lens of subaltern studies and feminist theory and examines how Dopdi's body and voice become sites of both oppression and assertion, challenging the intersections of caste, class, gender. Using theoretical frameworks from Spivak, Gramsci, and Judith Butler. This paper seeks to explore the interplay of gender, caste, class, and power in shaping subaltern agency taking into account the theoretical frameworks from feminist critics like Spivak, Gramsci, Judith Butler and so on. The analysis focuses on Dopdi's transformation from victim to rebel and offers a counter-narrative of subaltern as well as feminist resistance against patriarchal and colonial domination.

KEYWORDS: *Subaltern agency, Patriarchy, Gendered resistance, Intersectionality, Postcolonial oppression, Feminism, Body politics, Myth.*

Mahasweta Devi's short story "Draupadi" sets against the backdrop of the Naxalite Movement in West Bengal, India, the story reinterprets the mythological Draupadi from the Mahabharata as Dopdi Mejhen who is presented as both a victim as well as a rebel. Through the oppression and resistance of this tribal woman, Devi explores the intersection of gender, caste, class and politics in a postmodern context. Interestingly, by investigating the dynamics of state power and the resilience of the subalterns, the short story operates not merely as a narrative of marginalization but as a radical representation of subaltern resistance and assertion in which the body becomes both a site of violation and a means of defiance. The story, on the one hand, is a powerful exploration of the systemic exploitation of the marginalized people; on the other hand, it also presents a counter narrative of resistance against patriarchal and colonial oppression.

The term "subaltern," was first used by Antonio Gramsci, an Italian philosopher in his "Prison Notebooks" and by the term he refers to those groups

who are excluded from the dominant power structure. Critics like Gayatri Spivak, describes subalterns as groups in society who are socially, politically, and economically outside the hegemonic power structures. In *Draupadi*, Dopdi has been presented as a subaltern and she is triply marginalized – oppressed by caste, class and gender. subalternity in multiple ways: she is a tribal, a woman, poor, and a member of a revolutionary group. The state agencies view her, as an enemy and target her to crush any kind of protest or resilience. So, the resistance of Dopdi, who is marginalised in multiple ways, is really remarkable.

Spivak, in her essay "Can the Subaltern Speak?" questions whether the subaltern can truly find a voice within the discourse of power and is of the opinion that the voice of a subaltern remains unheard. Devi's narrative challenges this notion of Spivak. At the beginning of the narrative, readers find Dopdi as a helpless and voiceless figure, who is a victim oppressed by the state machinery and patriarchal violence. But as the story progresses, she transforms from a victim to a rebel against the state machinery

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and other such oppressive agencies. Instead of remaining passive, Dropdi registers her protest in a very radical and powerful way. So, through Dropdi and her astounding act of resistance, Devi presents a counter-point to Spivak's pessimistic argument in her famous essay "Can the Subaltern Speak?", illustrating the fact that even a subaltern can resistance in a very powerful and meaningful way instead of refusing to submit.

This story named "*Draupadi*" depicts the state as an oppressive entity that employs all its agencies to crush the oppressive movements of the marginal people. The state agencies consider the resistance of the marginal people not as a legitimate movement for their rights but a pugnacious activity and have no hesitation to crush the resistance movement of the tribal people in the most brutal way. The narrative exposes the brutal exercise of state violence upon the tribal people. The story presents Dropdi as a symbolic character who as a victim of state brutality. On the other hand, the character of Senanayak, the officer tasked with capturing Dropdi, is emblematic of this state brutality. He acts as a part of the state mechanism that operates systematically often resorting to force and violence to curb the movement as well as to silence dissent represents a rationalized brutality, one that uses systemic mechanisms to silence dissent. The state mechanism often employ propaganda to attach the tag of criminality against such political resistance of marginal communities and by abating the resistance as a law and order tries to validate their brutal exercise of state violence in suppressing the resistance of the subalterns.

This story depicts the brutal torture of Dropdi, the tribal woman, by the state machinery and torture clearly demonstrates the extremes to which Dropdi is not just arrested but she is repeatedly raped and she undergoes the double agonies – both physical and mental for being raped. Here state uses rape as a weapon to punish Dropdi for being defiant and this shows not only class based but also gender based oppression. Dropdi is repeatedly raped and her body demonstrates naked dominance over a subaltern- both on the basis of class and gender. The state even tries to mug Dropdi of her identity and humanity. But, what makes Dropdi so remarkable is her spirit of rebellion. She refuses to be silent and becomes a symbol of remonstrate and resistance by her act of defiance against the oppressive state mechanism.

Senanayak and his squads deploy harsh and inhumane tactics that reflect the systemic oppression directed at tribal people. These actions go beyond oppressing dissent-they aim to obliterate the identity and existence of these groups. Women like Dropdi become

unintentional symbols of remonstrate and resistance simply because they live beyond the boundaries of dominant social and political norms. Their suffering-through abduction, sexual violence, and assault-is not random but part of a broader institutional effort to assert control over the marginalized. In this way, Draupadi becomes a powerful denunciation of state-sanctioned violence, revealing how barbarity is legitimized under the pretext of preserving national order.

The denouement of the story "*Draupadi*" is very powerful as well as symbolic. Dropdi, who is naked and bleeding, confronts Senanayak, "*Draupadi*... stands up. She turns towards Senanayak and says, 'What's the use of clothes? You can strip me, but how can you clothe me again? You can't.'" The denouement of this story reminds one of Devi's play "*Mother of 1084*" where the protagonist Sujata voices her protest against the brutality of the state machinery at the end of the play.

In the denouement of the story, we see the body of Dropdi as the site of the most brutal violence on the one hand and through the agency of the most potent resistance on the other. Dropdi is naked but she refuses to be mortified, refuses to be silenced and also refuses to capitulate before the state machinery. By standing naked and defying her oppressor, she not only registers her protest but also reclaims her agency. Her radical way of resistance is a wake-up call for her community and disturbs the very fabric of the society. She refuses to cover her body-a body that has been violated by the state, but it is not an act of compliance but a declaration of defiance against the oppressive system.

This reckless act of Dropdi is really powerful and thought provoking and through this scene Devi renegotiates the issue of prestige and stigma associated with female nudity. In *The Mahabharata*, Draupadi's honor is defended by the divine intervention of Krishna during a public disrobing. But, in contrast, Devi's Dropdi has no divine protector at all. She shows herself as a defiant character who shakes off the stigma of nakedness and emerges as a rebel who even uses her nakedness as a form of protest so far unknown to those powers who sought to intimidate her.

The consequence of this act lies in its reversal of the gaze. Dropdi is raped, standing naked and in bleeding state, illustrated by Senanayak, expects that Dropdi after being raped and in her naked and bleeding state must be terrified, mortified and broken woman but to her utter distress Dropdi emerges as a figure of unyielding power and resistance. Dropdi who is stripped of clothing but not dignity, glares back

defiantly at the agent of the state, rendering him speechless and mystified. It seems, the subaltern does speak-not through language but through embodied resistance that disrupts the patriarchal and state-sanctioned norms of oppression.

This rebellious act transmutes what is traditionally seen as frailty into a form of power, opening the narrative to a feminist interpretation. Dopdi takes control of the space where she was assaulted, transforming it into a platform for asserting her agency. Her nakedness does not reflect ignominy; rather, it becomes a symbol of indestructible strength. In this reassessment, she challenges and expands the idea of female empowerment, especially in settings where typical modes of resistance are forbidden.

In this story myth has also played a crucial role suggesting the nature of oppression a woman has to face whether belongs to any age. Mahesweta Devi's "*Draupadi*" is also no exception as it hints at to Draupadi, one of the most important and controversial events of the epic are the disrobing of Draupadi in front of all. The scene shows that Draupadi is disrobed and humiliated before all men present in the court but she is saved from this demeaning situation by the divine interference of Lord Krishna. But, in Devi's narrative, Dopdi finds no divine support to deliver her from her perilous situation rather she relies on her own courage and persistence. She resists in a radical way instead of seeking divine or any form of aid. The story's mythic vibrancy adds a layer of intertextuality that deepens its political influence. So, "*Draupadi*" recontextualises the myth within a present political structure and by doing so she seeks to subvert the traditional depiction of the vulnerable woman. In Devi's narrative, Dopdi becomes a symbol of contemporary defiance. one who confronts the oppressor and in addition, awakens the readers to be aware of the reality and to rise against any sort of oppression and discrimination. This subversion of ancient mythology challenges cultural smugness and insists on new narratives of emancipation rooted in lived realities rather than divine intervention.

Furthermore, Devi's choice to name her protagonist "*Draupadi*" serves a deliberate purpose beyond mere symbolism. By citing a prominent figure from mythology, she creates a powerful bridge between historical and contemporary realities, blending the sacred with the subversive. This narrative approach requires readers to recognize the persistent nature of oppression and violence against women across time and to critically reflect on the dormancy in societal progress regarding gender justice.

In this narrative, Mahasweta Devi altered the discourse on women's agency in subaltern politics.

Dopdi Mejhén does not comply with the standard image of an activist-she neither addresses masses nor writes ideological tracts. Instead, her political presence is communicated through her bodily actions and deliberate refusals. Even when silenced by structural violence, her body becomes a text of resistance, refusing erasure (Devi 29).

Her final act upsets dominant narrative expectations. There is no redeemer to deliver her, no fatal end that marks her as a martyr. She endures, holding her ground against her aggressors. This endurance is not passive endurance but a conscious defiance that undermines state authority and challenges the readers with a mode of resistance grounded in silent but potent dissent. Her stance complicates the idea of political agency, which is often equated with public speech or leadership roles, by offering a counterexample: insurgency embedded in lived, bodily experience. Devi's portrayal also recast trauma. Rather than allowing suffering to conclude the narrative, the text insists on the persistence of agency within suffering. Here, survival becomes a political act, and in enduring, the subaltern can reclaim subjectivity (Spivak 88). This ethic of survival resists the totalizing power of oppression, asserting that even in the sequel of dehumanization, the possibility of reclamation remains.

From a feminist perspective, Draupadi stands as a direct challenge to patriarchal scripts that cast women as passive victims. Dopdi's resolute defiance following sexual violence dismantles such portrayals. In the climactic moment when she confronts her captors unclothed, she refuses to accept the shame they seek to impose, demanding that they witness the outcome of their own brutality (Devi 33). Her declaration transforms the scene into both a personal triumph and a public indictment of state power.

Judith Butler's concept of gender performativity-where gender is produced through socially repeated acts-offers a critical lens here (Butler 34). By rejecting the performance of the "ashamed victim," Dopdi refuses the patriarchal narrative of concealment and silence. Her nudity becomes a deliberate political statement, revealing the violence of the state rather than her own vulnerability.

Her resistance further exposes how female suffering is often commodified within nationalist or patriarchal discourse. By wielding her wounded body as a truth-bearing weapon rather than a symbol of defeat, Dopdi asserts full narrative and bodily sovereignty. In Devi's telling, feminist assertion is inseparable from political consciousness; it is enacted not through rhetorical flourish but through embodied defiance.

To sum up, Mahasweta Devi's *Draupadi* is a profound exploration of subaltern resistance. It throws light on the struggles of tribal communities in India while engaging with broader questions of gender, power, and agency. Through Dopdi Mejhen, Devi creates a character who transcends victimhood and embodies the spirit of resistance. Her silence, her nudity, and her defiance are louder than any speech, asserting that even in the face of extreme violence, the subaltern does speak.

In a world where marginalized voices are often distorted, *Draupadi* serves as both a political indictment and a call to consciousness. It forces us to recognize the humanity, the strength, and the resistance of those who exist outside the margins of power structure. Moreover, it demands that readers and critics alike expand their understanding of resistance beyond the conventional political arena, acknowledging the radical potential of bodily defiance and symbolic gestures. Ultimately, *Draupadi* compels a reconsideration of how we understand oppression and agency. It is a story of immense brutality, but also one of tremendous strength. Mahasweta Devi's reworking of the mythic into the material, the divine into the human, renders Dopdi not as a footnote in someone else's history, but as the author of her own resistance.

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